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The Watchful Eye: Surveillance, Social Norms and Ethical Quandaries in Recent Malayalam Cinema

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Abstract:

A surge in surveillance in the early twenty-first century has culminated in the now widely accepted delineation of present-day society as a “surveillance society.” This steady rise in surveillance technologies in public spaces and even at homes primarily neutered the dynamics of human interaction and behaviour. Furthermore, surveillance is a subject in film, television and social media. Subsequently, surveillance has become a core aspect of the modern-day visual culture and life more commonly. This paper aims to explore surveillance as a narrative method for examining the themes of social control, social and psychological consequences, and ethical dilemmas, particularly in recent Malayalam movies. This paper argues that *Footage* and *Sookshmadarshini* employ domestic surveillance as a critique of normalised voyeurism, exposing how ethical boundaries are blurred in the pursuit of curiosity, control, and perceived safety. Panopticon theory, Surveillance society, and other surveillance theories are used to support the statements in this paper.

Keywords: Surveillance, Observation, Power, Ethics, Society.

Behind the lens of every camera, within the code of every app and in the shadow of every streetlight, there lies a crucial question: Who is watching and to what extent? Surveillance—a close watch kept over someone or something has now shifted from a device of state security to a ubiquitous reality that touches virtually every facet of present-day life. The proliferation of surveillance as a subject in films and television is not just a representation of the increased prominence of surveillance in society. Instead, it indicates a change in the perspective of surveillance. Traditionally, surveillance referred to police or government monitoring. However, in contemporary society, it has become an integral part of everyday life. More than just cameras or technical systems, surveillance now functions as a framework through which reality is interpreted.

As surveillance becomes embedded in everyday life, it prompts questions about where legitimate surveillance ends and voyeuristic invasion begins. In this decade, the rise in popularity of reality television has brought unprecedented levels of change into the world of entertainment. Clay Calvert, in his insightful work, “Voyeur Nation,” examines this trend. He highlights the insidious growth of voyeurism as a cultural force. Calvert presents the vital concept of “mediated voyeurism,” which defines the public’s voracious desire for programs and images that expose the ostensibly authentic and unguarded lives of others. Calvert opines, “Mediated voyeurism refers to the consumption of revealing images of and information about others’ real and unguarded lives, often yet not always for purposes of entertainment but frequently at the expense of privacy and discourse, through the means of the mass media and internet” (Calvert 2-3). This consumption—driven by a yearning for entertainment—often comes at the expense of an individual’s privacy. Society has normalized the invasive nature of social media and reality shows, subverting the binaries between public and private spheres.

This cultural shift, in which surveillance becomes a primary form of entertainment, is incrementally depicted in contemporary Malayalam cinemas.

This voyeuristic gaze has found compelling expression in regional cinema, where filmmakers interrogate the psychological and social implications. Recent Malayalam films such as *Footage* and *Sookshmadarshini* (2024) lucidly portray society's tendency to intrude into others' lives—whether they are neighbours, companions, or strangers. These films capture the essence of everyday life within the typical neighbourhoods thereby altering the “ordinary” to a venue of voyeuristic inspection. They deeply analyse the subtle ways in which the individuals observe, analyse and inevitably become entangled in the lives of those around them. These movies highlight how the close vicinity of neighbours along with the technological advancements create an environment of ease where the tendency to observe and interpret is high. These films act as a mirror to society, echoing the escalating normalization of mediated voyeurism and provoking the audience to ponder the ethical implications of the intrusive cultural trend. Moreover, they portray how ordinary people in their daily surroundings are vulnerable to the same voyeuristic impulses that fuel the popularity of reality shows. As a result, the distinction between screen and reality gets diluted.

Sookshmadarshini, being released in 2024, directed by M.C Jithin and written by Libin T.B and Athul Ramachandran, is a black comedy thriller movie which portrays Priyadarshini, a diligent homemaker with a keen sense of observation. She becomes increasingly dubious of her neighbour Manuel's unusual behaviour. Manuel, along with his uncle Roy and Dr. John, murders his sister Diana because of her sexuality. Driven by curiosity and her suspicions about the constant disappearance of Manuel's mother, Grace, Priya embarks on a covert investigation, gradually gathering evidence and connecting the clues. This pursuit ultimately leads Priya to uncover the disturbing truth about Manuel, enabling her to rescue Diana's girlfriend, Aditi,

from an impending murder. However, her unrelenting curiosity also sets in motion a chain of events that results in unintended harm.

Released in 2024 and directed by Saiju Sreedharan, *Footage* is another such film in which surveillance is portrayed in its most extreme form. In our society, many cases are unveiled with the help of CCTV footage or other camera visuals that people capture in their surroundings. This movie portrays a YouTube vlogger couple living in an apartment, always craving to know what is happening in others' apartments. Their voyeuristic nature is precise from the initial scenes where they find pleasure in watching the intimate sexual scenes of a couple in the opposite building. This curiosity also drives them to follow a mysterious woman living down the hall. Their curiosity leads them to go as far as following her into the woods to reveal more about her mysterious identity and personality. They follow this thread of curiosity more profound into their investigation, leading them to experience some uncomfortable things that test their resolve and blend the lines between reality and the unknown.

This section argues that surveillance as portrayed in these films symbolizes a shift from a means of care to the expression of power, illustrating Michel Foucault's concept of disciplinary control within domestic and communal spaces. Surveillance is customarily regarded disdainfully and often with fear, in the early 1990s. The act of informal, localised surveillance, such as neighbourhood peeping, was widely considered a social transgression, regardless of the established presence of more comprehensive surveillance. Reciprocal anxiety of being watched distinguished this period, wherein individuals feared being subjected to the equivalent scrutiny they might impose. Remarkably, there was a relative absence of omnipresent, self-generated public exposure of private lives. On the contrary, present-day society exhibits a dramatic turn towards the normalization of privacy intrusion, facilitated by the ubiquitous practice of voluntary self-disclosure on social media platforms. Consequently, a culture of voyeurism and exhibitionism has emerged, wherein individuals actively engage in both watching and being

watched, signifying a fundamental transformation in societal perceptions of privacy and publicness.

The protagonists in *Sookshmadarshini*, particularly Priya, the meticulous microbiologist, and the couples in *Footage* engage in covert surveillance that beyond idle curiosity, becomes a powerful tool of social control and a form of power play. This act of surreptitious surveillance allows them to have agency in (socially) controlling others' lives or subject(s) by monopolizing their social space without their knowledge or consent. In basically pilfering their subjects by collecting evidence and reconstructing their stories (to the extent that they are defined by their subjects), they produce a distorted power dynamic. This distortion stems from the observed individuals' vulnerability; they are unaware of the scrutiny they are under, leaving them defenceless against the judgements and potential interventions of their unseen observers.

Jeremy Bentham's 1787 Panopticon design, a circular prison with a central watchtower, established a system of power through the inmates' constant potential for surveillance, even when actual observation was uncertain (Bentham 64-68). The aforementioned scenario is discernible in the movies *Footage* and *Sookshmadarshini*. Each apartment unit functions as a distinct spatial cell within a carceral construction, establishing a panoptic framework wherein the observers assume the role of surveillant agents. At the same time, the remaining inhabitants are reduced to passive subjects. The powerful gaze exchanged by Priya towards Manuel on multiple occasions serves as this exertion of power over Manuel.

Michael Foucault further developed the idea in his book "Discipline and Punish." Foucault says: "They are like so many cages, so many small theatres, in which each actor is alone, perfectly individualised and constantly visible. The panoptic mechanism arranges spatial unities that make it possible to see constantly and to recognize immediately" (200). Through the portrayal of a close-knit neighbourhood, *Footage* and *Sookshmadarshini* construct a social

space reminiscent of panoptic structures, fostering a pervasive sense of social surveillance. The inhabitants living in this community maintain a comprehensive awareness of the daily activities within the immediate vicinity. Within the narrative of *Sookshmadarshini*, Priya has initial scepticism on Manuel's assertion that Ammachi has Alzheimer's following her absence and subsequent discovery. She attempts to share her doubts with Sulu, her neighbour. Upon observing Sulu's dissent, Priya urges Sulu to listen to the whistles of the pressure cooker and reports that it will not exceed four whistles. At this point she junctures, "*Ucha aavaarayi, Manuelinte veettil kanji vevikkan vachirikkuva. Ithu njan sthiram kelkkunatha*" (It is almost noon now. Rice gruel is being cooked at Manuel's house. I hear this regularly.) (*Sookshmadarshini* 48:03-10).

Foucault posits that "Panopticon is a marvellous machine which, whatever use one may wish to put it to, produces homogenous effects of power" (202). *Footage* and *Sookshmadarshini* both explore the act of surveillance with differing motivations and consequences. In *Footage*, the couples are curious to uncover the obscurity of the "mysterious lady". This prompts them to employ various invasive methods, seeking a sense of power through knowledge acquisition. Whereas, Priya's surveillance in *Sookshmadarshini* is driven by a concern for Ammachi's safety, which is evident when she expresses her doubt, "*Ini ammachide missinginte purakil Manuel thanne ayirikkuvo?*" (Will Manuel be the reason behind Ammachi's missing?) (*Sookshmadarshini* 1:04:13-15). This concern turns into an exercise of power over Manuel, which forces her to play a detective role to investigate Manuel's intentions.

Foucault also includes: "He is seen, but he does not see: he is the object of information, never a subject in communication" (200). In both movies, the watcher is hidden and observing the activities of the person in doubt. They are fearless as they have the confidence that they will not be looked back. For Priyadarshini, Manuel and her other neighbours are objects of information. She is a constant and keen observer. It is demonstrated in a dialogue with her

neighbour Sulu when she articulates her doubts regarding Manuel's report on Ammachi's Alzheimer's. She states. "*Iruttathu bed switch idaan ariyaam, tankil vellam nirayumpol motor off akkan ariyaam, purathu ninnu varumpol cherupp polum oori idaan marakkarilla.*" (She knows how to turn on the bed switch in the dark, she knows to switch off the motor when the water tank gets full, she never even forgets to take off the slippers when she enters the house) (*Sookshmadarshini* 47:20-26).

In *Footage*, the relationship between the voyeuristic couple and the 'mysterious lady' shows a stark power imbalance; she is an object of information with no power to participate in the communicative act, an object of spectacle to consume, a puzzle to be solved, and not someone who can meaningfully contribute to a dialogic act. The couple is insatiably curious, turning their balcony into a spatial affordance to consume her life vicariously; they cannot atomise her as an object of information. The act of voyeurism shows the uninvited face of their curiosity in her life; she can never insert herself into that relationship, and their gaze is focused entirely and viewing her entirely as a force of interest. Their interest is defined by a 'spirit of enquiry.' This objectification culminates in a blatant violation of her privacy when they, aided by their maid, trespass into her home. This invasion transcends simple observation, becoming an act of forceful appropriation of her personal space and a blatant display of their perceived entitlement. They treat her home as an extension of the observation - a space both to experience and colonize. In that act of exploration and discovery, the subjectivity she could possess is reconstructed by the couples, and she becomes a kind of object for their use. The mysterious lady's lack of permission and understanding demonstrates an asymmetry of power, marks a danger of unbridled curiosity, and shows the ethical considerations involved when people become observation objects.

Jean-Paul Sartre discusses the constitution of subjectivity in his seminal work, "Being and Nothingness." Sartre argues, "What I grasp immediately when I hear the branches breaking

behind me is not that someone is there but that I am vulnerable, that I have a body that can be hurt, that I am occupying a place and that I cannot in any circumstance escape from the space in which I am, defenceless—in short, that I am seen” (382). Manuel, being the object of gaze, suddenly transcends to the observer as Priya enters his premise, thereby shifting the locus of the gaze. Priya’s hierarchical power diminishes, and she becomes the subject of observation. This alteration in the power dynamic is discernible in her vocal register, betraying a disruption of her former authoritative stance.

Alfred Hitchcock's 'Rear Window' also involves a similarly situated protagonist, L.B Jeffries, which is reminiscent of Priya and the couples in the selected films. Jeffries' obsession with viewing his neighbours provides an interesting angle to explore the nature of surveillance further, especially as seen through the dialogue between Jeffries and his girlfriend, Lisa. Jeffries's easy dismissal of his voyeuristic acts as 'spying' and the labelling of himself and those like him as 'peeping Toms' indicates just how ingrained the understanding of surveillance as harmful and ethically wrong is in our society. His degeneration of the objects of his observation, referring to them as "bugs under a glass", suggests the dehumanization that comes with surveillance and his firing wish to observe them. The metaphor itself makes clear the asymmetry associated with looking. The looked upon are rendered passive recipients of a controlling gaze and are stripped of their agency and privacy. This antagonistic interpretation of surveillance follows the normative definition of surveillance as a top-down power structure, a one-way street from the watcher to the watched. This definition is rooted in our cultural psyche, as shown in familiar metaphors, 'Big Brother' and the 'Panopticon'. Both metaphors illustrate a vertical, institutionalised power relation. Indeed the gaze of the watcher, be it that of a repressive state or a building that was intended to surveil and control behaviour, is intended to dominate and regulate the behaviours of the watched.

The Big Brother metaphor, derived from George Orwell's 1984, implies some sense of immediate, oppressive surveillance: that individuals have the sense of being under surveillance at all times which moves individuals toward self-regulation and conformity. The Panopticon (Foucault, 1979) makes a similar argument by suggesting that individuals 'will' self-regulate and appear obedient if they have a sense that they may be under surveillance. Both metaphors, and Janice Jeffries's informal and casual yet illuminating language, suggest that surveillance - in its traditional sense- is a form of control, by way of exercising power through visible, and often invisible, forms of observation. Both metaphors suggest (in their essence) that observation diminishes the observed individual's agency and turns them into passive subjects in a system that serves hardly in any regard to regulating their behaviour but instead controls their behaviour.

While surveillance represents a top-down surveying approach, its conceptual analogue, "sousveillance", suggests a democratic inversion of the traditional power dynamic. Coined by researcher Steve Mann in the 1990s, sousveillance – from the French "sous" (below) and "veiller" (to watch), empowers citizens to record and monitor authority figures using personal technologies. In Footage, the agents reflect sousveillance by documenting their encounters with the mysterious female figure and using that documentation as evidence for their collaborative, participatory monitoring efforts.

The introduction of new surveillance methods recurrently catalyses debates filled with dystopian visions from popular culture. The characters in Footage and Sookshmarshini justify their actions through a blend of boredom and an innate fascination with the lives of others. The couples in Footage are confined to their apartment due to the COVID pandemic. As an escape from their mundane existence, they find themselves drawn to the lives of neighbours. According to Leon Festinger, it is not merely a habit. He claims that "individuals derive self-worth by comparing themselves to others, which he terms as "social-comparison

theory.” In his paper “A Theory of Social Comparison Processes,” he proposes how “individuals evaluate their opinions and abilities by comparing themselves to others to reduce uncertainty in these domains and learn how to define the self” (Festinger 118). Priya’s initial happiness and excitement in *Sookshmarshini* at her successful interview outcome is instantly diminished upon knowing that Steffy has also passed the interview. Steffy announces the information in their WhatsApp group named “Ladies First”, and in turn, Priya immediately informs her success in the same. This underscores a tendency for social comparison wherein Priya’s self-evaluation is contingent upon the performance of her peers. Her subsequent offer of a treat for her successful training interview, along with her wedding anniversary, can be interpreted as an attempt to assert her social dominance or to occupy a position of superiority within her peer group.

Priya justifies her act by stating, “*Ayalde full kallatharavum polichadukkanam.*” (All of his lies must be exposed) (*Sookshmarshini* 1:28:33-36). Her concern for *Ammachi* (Grace) develops into doubts about murder or kidnap. This in turn sparks a curiosity in her, which she cannot resist. Whereas in *Footage*, from the beginning, the male protagonist interrogates the female about her constant observation and curiosity about the lady living downstairs. In an instance where the maid reports to them of the day’s taciturn nature, the female protagonist shows her curiosity, “*Ivar aaraayiriikkum alle? Chechiyodu polum mindaandirikkanamenkil.*” (Who is she really? If she is not even talking to the maid.) (*Footage* 1:21:47-51). The male protagonist responds by discouraging her curiosity, stating, “*Avar aarenkilum ayikkotte. Namukkentha?... Avaraayi avarde paadaayi, nammal enthina veruthe avarude privacy keru thalayidunne.*” (Let it be whoever... Why should we care?... Why should we peep into her privacy? (*Footage* 1:21:51-22:01). The female protagonist counters with, “*Pakshe enikkishtama athokke.*” (But I like such things) (*Footage* 1:22:02-04). It reveals her fondness for surveillance and, potentially, a transgression of social boundaries.

Furthermore, the male's voyeuristic tendencies are visible from the first scene. During observation of a sexual encounter occurring in a neighbouring apartment, he says, "Ore position, ore expression." (Same position, same expression.) (*Footage* 00:47-50). This initial scene sets the stage for his character's pattern of voyeurism. The female's subsequent participation, wherein she predicts the couple's actions with, "*Ini avar eneekum, ennit oru otta kettipidutham, ennittavalu pinnilekkoru valachilaayirikkum.*" (Now they will get up, then they will hug. After that, the girl will bend backwards.) (*Footage* 01:28-40) highlights her involvement in voyeurism.

Surveillance raises a fundamentally troubling ethical dilemma: its ability to assist comes at the cost of its ability to make intrusive privacy violations. Cinematic endeavours of Saiju Sreedharan as seen in *Footage*, and M.C. Jithin as evident in *Sookshmadarshini*, apparently portray this conflict. It highlights the ambiguous dichotomy between observation for reasonable and voyeuristic intrusion. The actions of the characters raise questions about the ethics of surveillance. Is a secret observation through the intrusion of the privacy of others justifiable when it leads to the unveiling of a crime? Although the films showcase moral ambiguity inherent in the situation, they deliberately avoid a straightforward solution.

For *Priyadarshini*, the act of observing others is simply a job potentially aroused from her job as a microbiologist. Priya displays a diminished concern for ethical boundaries, even when her husband, Antony, attempts to redirect her inquisitive nature. Following *Ammachi's* recovery from her disappearance, Manuel attributes her actions to Alzheimer's disease. However, Priya remains doubtful, and she expresses this to Antony when he shares the emotional scenes in the police station. She articulates, "*Alzheimer's ulla aalkk ithokke orma kaanuvo? Ithokke ullathaano?*" (Would a person with Alzheimer's remember all these things? Are all these even true?) (*Sookshmadarshini* 41:56-42:01). She explicitly states her disbelief in this and poses a question, "*Pinne ividunnu railway station vare enganeya poyathennu oru idea kittathe.*" (I have

no idea how did she got from here to the railway station) (*Sookshmadarshini* 42:24-28). Antony responds, “*Enthaayaalum thirichu kittiyallo.*” (Anyway, we got her back. Right?) (42:28-30).

Recognising the inherent risk in following the lady, the boy in Footage inquired, “*Ithentho preshnam pidicha parupaadiya. Namukk ivide nilkkenda. Thirichu poyaalo?*” (This seems like some huge trouble. Shall we leave this and go back?) (*Footage* 1:38:19-25). However, the girl, driven by a desire for knowledge, countered, “*Entha avarde parupadinnu nokkaallo... Namukkavare follow cheythaalo?* (Let us get to know what their plan... Shall we follow them?) (*Footage* 1:38:35-40).

A dilemma arises because it is only possible to know if a crime has been committed after the fact. It is a peculiar situation if the ethical soundness of a given action cannot be determined before it is done since it reduces the key ethical aspect of responsibility to a matter of chance based on more or less well-founded suspicions. This issue is brought up in both movies by the characters surrounding the protagonists. Antony cautions Priya regarding her persistent nature, stating, “*Priye, ninak pande ullatha. Oru karyam manasil keru kazhinjaal athu vidaan bhayankara paadaa... Athu ninte ammachi onnumallallo...Nee athu vidu...ini athinte purake pokanda, namukk randaallkkum athaanu nallathu.*” (Priya, you have had this habit for a long time. Once something gets into your mind, you will not let it go...It is not your mother or anything...You let it go...Do not go after it anymore that is better for both of us.) (*Sookshmadarshini* 1:26:22-43). This conversation denotes a clear bent for prying pursuits in Priya's previous behaviour. Priya refuses Antony's warning and still intends to try to investigate despite the warning. This pursuit, while ultimately leading to Aditi's rescue from a potential murder, also precipitates Priya's downfall.

This predicament is also evident when her friend Jesna, a microbiologist, warns her about the impending danger associated with the case. She says, “*Di ithentho kuzhappam pidicha*

casseaa... Nee thanna sampleilu acidum human bone cellsum undarnu..dhe vendathathinu thalayidathe nee policeine vilich parayan nokk.” (This seems like some kind of problematic case...The sample you gave had acid and human bone cells...Look, do not interfere unnecessarily, you better try to inform the police.) (*Sookshmadarshini* 2:07:04-12). However, Priya is not deterred; she becomes even more curious and determined to investigate.

The discussion between two characters in *Footage* picks up on the inherent tension between knowledge seeking and the potential consequences of unchecked investigation. When the male protagonist states, “*Baby listen to me, ee caseil nammal allenkil thane avishyathiladhikam valli pidich vachittund... ithinte purake poyal evide chennu avasanikkumenn kandariyanam.”* (We have already faced many issues with this case...we could not predict what is going to happen next) (*Footage* 1:39:40-55), marks a critical juncture in their pursuit. The uncertainty conveyed by “*kandariyanam evide chennu nilkumenn,”* reflects the unpredictability of investigative endeavours, particularly when it is enigmatic or potentially dangerous subjects. This uncertainty should be acknowledged as it recognises that we are at some limits of their control and we cannot predict any consequences fortuitously.

The final question posed by the male protagonist is, “So I am asking you one last time. Are you sure?” (*Footage* 1:39:56-40:00)—functions as an important moment of decision-making. The question acknowledges the process they have gone through and emphasizes the finality of the decision, which entails a strong and unwavering commitment from his partner. Her confirmatory nod, a nonverbal response, signifies an agreement, but it is a decisive agreement. It implies that both understand the possible consequences and are firmly dedicated to moving forward. The concerned tone of the male protagonist with the unwavering response of the female protagonist signals some balance between caution and dedication. Moreover, the male protagonist serves as the voice of reason, urging a careful consideration of the risks. In contrast, the female protagonist embodies a more unwavering commitment to the pursuit of truth. These

interactions highlight the difficulties of working together and figuring out the potential balance of risks they are willing to take.

The rapid pace of technological progress has undoubtedly fuelled the conversation surrounding surveillance and its implications on personal privacy. George Orwell's renowned novel, "1984", represents a chilling premonition, introducing the famous image of 'Big Brother', the all-seeing and all-knowing eye of observation. Orwell's novel depicts a world in which facets of human choice and freedom are dismantled through endless observation, with outcomes driven by fear and reduction in an individual's characteristics. The dystopian description of society provided in 'Nineteen Eighty-Four' is particularly powerful in light of today's reality in which there are tools made possible through technology that create deeper levels of observation and data collection. Finally, the films in this study echo such dystopian concerns through their accounts detailing surveillance that becomes catastrophic because of its capacity to consume and become an obsession.

The protagonists, with insatiable curiosity, have an analogous role and subject their world into a microcosm of Orwell's Panopticon where the possibility of observation engenders a sensation of perpetual observation. This maelstrom of obsession produces a vicious mix of curiosity and moral imagining that dissolves the division between appropriate inquiry and unwarranted voyeurism. The protagonist's relentless pursuit, often under the guise of acting morally, erodes ethical spectrums. The films portray how the accessibility of technological surveillance makes it easy for borders to fade, turning incidental observation into a potentially dangerous incursion of boundaries. The protagonists, while assuming benevolent intentions, ultimately reveal the nature of unchecked curiosity and the potential for surveillance to be a means of exerting power. The films function as a contemporary means of reasoning against Orwell's dystopic vision, where the pursuit of apparent knowledge and observing an exceedance of liberties becomes a

disvalue in replacing attempts at moral or ethical observance with weakened attempts to present protagonists with these truths.

The movies *Footage* and *Sookshmadarshini* interrogate the role of the observer by collapsing the rigid boundaries between passive observation on the one hand and active participation on the other. Initially, Priyadarshini in *Sookshmadarshini* is content to watch her neighbours from a distance simply. However, as she suspects that Manuel is exhibiting some type of problematic behaviour that connects him to *Ammachi's* disappearance, she becomes fascinated with their lives and begins to take more invasive steps, including visiting his house often and sharing information in their gossip WhatsApp group. Whereas, in *Footage*, the couples can be seen from the beginning obsessed with watching the lives of others. It is evident when the girl says, “*Ravile thane thudangiyallo avante scene pidutham.*” (His voyeurism started right from the morning.) (*Footage* 00:58-1:00). This voyeuristic trajectory deepens when they join in spying on the life of the woman below their flat, and it becomes more extreme when they break into the woman's house with the help of their common maid. It makes us question the nature of surveillance and whether observation itself ever crosses a line into harmful or unethical behaviour.

The films complicate the observer even further by stripping the observer of the illusion of being objective. Priyadarshini, for instance, initially perceives herself as a detached, impartial witness, documenting what is happening in her community, but maintains that illusion of objectivity only so long as she is detached from the context of *Ammachi's* well-being. Once, her visceral suspicion of Manuel starts to take form in her inquiry, “*Ini ammachide missinginte purakil Manuel ayirikkumo?*” (Could Manuel be behind *Ammachi's* disappearance?) (*Sookshmadarshini* 1:04:13-15), her objectively-positioned observations succumb to her subjective concern. Once seemingly clinical, her perceptions become increasingly coloured by

her personal biases and emotional attachments. This transformation underscores the inherent fallacy of pure objective observation.

The films illustrate how even the best-intentioned observers cannot help but be influenced by their inclinations, desires and worries. The intrusion of their subjectivity will affect how they interpret and understand the events they are observing. Priyadarshini's transition from dispassionate observer to concerned investigator demonstrates the ease with which personal involvement can distort perception. The story suggests that what an observer 'sees' is not merely a reflection of reality but a product of their subjective lens. It complicates the idea that the act of observation can be entirely neutral, emphasising the relationship between perception and subjectivity. In demonstrating that subjectivity directly shapes interpretation, the films raise important concerns regarding the validity of 'truth' seen through an observer's account and the limitations of human objectivity.

These films reveal cautionary tales of dangers associated with unquestioned curiosity. This curiosity is not benign but an obsessive-compulsive interest that often takes characters into dangerous places. The voyeurism of the couples and Priyadarshini are not simply entertainment; instead, they are how they are thrown into suspicion and danger. The act of peeping into others' lives that began for amusement quickly becomes an obsession. That obsession leads them to a possible murder plot, which ultimately entraps them rather than empowers them. Each time they attempted to intervene based on a self-righteous sense that they could perceive wrongs, they were met with resistance and growing threats as a result. This plot line acts as a strong cautionary tale, warning against the temptations of deep involvement in the lives of others. It showcases the risks associated with intruding into matters that are not one's own, highlighting how the creeping nature leads to hazardous consequences.

The erosion of personal autonomy is one of the most significant impacts of constant surveillance. When a person becomes aware that they are constantly being observed, they may alter their behaviour to adhere to the perceived expectations. Michel Foucault's concept of the Panopticon aligns with this notion. He says, "Visibility is a trap" (200). Constant monitoring can influence our self-discipline. It also restricts the freedom of an individual, which results in anxiety. Moreover, it can also lead to a state of paranoia and develop distrust. David Lyon develops the notion of a "Surveillance society." He posits, "Surveillance changes the way we behave. Under observation, we act less freely and are more inclined to follow expected patterns." As soon as Manuel, in *Sookshmadarshini*, becomes aware that he is being observed constantly, his demeanour changes. He was stricken by a wave of apprehension, which left him feeling tensed. It is patently clear when he is called upon by his uncle as soon as Priya gets into his house. He utters, "*Aval ipol enthina angottu kettiyeduthathu?*" (Why the hell is she going in there?) (*Sookshmadarshini* 54:21-23).

Psychology researchers from the University of Technology Sydney have researched the psychological effects of constant surveillance. The results posit, that "when people know they are under surveillance it generates an automatic response of heightened awareness of being watched" (University of Technology Sydney). Additionally, they have learned that "hypersensitivity to eye gaze in mental health conditions like psychosis and social anxiety disorder where individuals hold irrational beliefs or preoccupations with the idea of being watched" (University of Technology Sydney).

Surveillance has developed from the material to the spatial and now to networks. The ethical considerations of observing others without consent have intensified relevance in a world dominated by digital surveillance. The simultaneous release of *Sookshmadarshini* and *Footage* in 2024 allows for a converging examination of the ethical consequences of voyeurism in the digital age. The prevalence of voluntary self-disclosure on social media platforms resulted in

a significant shift towards normalizing privacy invasion. The contemporary landscape of social media, marked by a seemingly endless stream of daily life experiences shared through platforms such as Snapchat, Instagram, and Facebook, has produced a fascinating paradox in personal privacy: individuals are willingly sharing intimate aspects of their private lives with everyone, while at the same time, they wish to see the intimate details of others' lives, especially of their followers. This dichotomy raises fundamental questions about the changing conception of privacy in a digital era.

The unceasing flow of personal updates, from even the most mundane details of our lives to significant aspects of our lives, suggests a change in normative behaviours. What used to be the act of sharing with close confidantes has been replaced with a performative public act. The performance/unveiling of one's digital self for usage and consideration by a global audience—our friends or acquaintances hardly matters at this stage. This phenomenon prompts us to consider whether the inherent value of privacy has diminished or if it has simply been redefined in the context of digital connectivity.

The ease with which we can access and share information has created a culture of transparency. The constant flood of notifications and updates instil a feeling of being watched/observed as individuals play both viewer and subject in our ongoing performances. This raises concerns about the dissolution of a sense of private identity, as the fluidity of living in a space where privacy is seemingly a negotiable commodity becomes synonymous with performance driven by social engagement and validation. The growing imperative of social validation, a characteristic of human nature, combined with the addictive form of social engagement, propels us to share and observe at the same time; and thus, continues the cycle, compounded and the definition of public/private is further confused. This presents a pressing concern as we evaluate our increasingly communal ownership of our online footprint.

As noted in Shoshana Zuboff's work "The Age of Surveillance Capitalism," "social media is a marketplace that trades exclusively human futures... Those markets have produced the trillions of dollars that have made the internet companies the richest companies in the history of humanity" (Zuboff). The potential for surveillance expands as the technology continues to evolve, creating a complicated landscape. Artificial intelligence and data analytics allow for unrivalled levels of monitoring. Zuboff asserts, "Surveillance capitalism unilaterally claims human experience as free raw material for translation into behavioural data" (Zuboff). This not only impacts individual privacy but also the foundation of autonomy and consent.

Indeed, both films act as potent narrative vehicles to reveal the complex relationship between unrestrained curiosity and omnipresent surveillance and the extended implications of both actions. These cinematic explorations transcend mere entertainment. They are critical social commentaries that address the power dynamics that emerge when we observe others. Observation can be a passive process, though it can quickly become a subtle, yet active, means of social control. By showcasing the protagonists' descent into obsessive observation, the morality of invading others' privacy and how knowledge-seeking can easily become an overt exercise of power is exposed. Moreover, it explains the social and psychological cost and the draining nature of monitoring or being monitored constantly, often in perpetuity.

The films emphasize the possibility that paranoia, anxiety and suspicion can leak into our social behaviours as we become more aware of our capacity for gazing unseen. They also reveal the psychological burden placed on the observers as they become consumed by their distrust and anxiety, ultimately confusing the boundaries of fact and fiction. In the end, the stories encourage us to be thoughtful about the ethical concerns of our voyeur habits and technology and their amplification of our desire to look. They serve as mirrors and ground contemporary anxieties around privacy and control in a connected world.

CONCLUSION

Surveillance studies not only provide a helping hand to understand the complexities of new and different forms of surveillance but also help to understand the changing power dynamics in society. Living in a 'Surveillance Society' has led to new, different and extreme forms of power and control. Priyadarshini and the couples are an exceptional example of the contemporary society where peering into other's lives is considered a habit. Especially as social media advances and our real-world lives are increasingly surveilled, there is a challenge with our ability to separate security from intrusion. The convenience of being interconnected comes at a steep price: our privacy, our freedom, and perhaps most importantly, our humanity. The recent Malayalam movies *Footage* and *Sookshmarshini* provide a clear depiction of a modern-day society where privacy is at stake. The chilling reality remains as, George Orwell poignantly expressed, "Big Brother is watching you."

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